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CONTENTS

ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF MINING REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS IN THE ENFORCEMENT OF HEALTH AND SAFETY REGULATIONS FOR ARTISANAL AND SMALL-SCALE MINING IN NIGERIA	1 - 17
<i>Okoronkwo Scholastica, Ogba Michael Chinonso, and Otu Cyril Chibuzo</i>	
GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS OF MALARIA INCIDENCES IN BADE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, YOBE STATE NIGERIA	18-32
<i>Usur, H.G., Yakudima, I.I. and Mustapha, A.</i>	
ANALYSIS OF VEGETATION COVER CHANGES USING NORMALIZED DIFFERENCE VEGETATION INDEX (NDVI) IN BIRNIN KEBBI, NIGERIA	33-49
<i>Ismail Usman Kaoje and Ishiaku Ibrahim</i>	
INLAND WATERWAYS TRANSPORTATION AND CHANGING URBAN MORPHOLOGY OF METROPOLITAN LAGOS, NIGERIA	50-66
<i>Ayanrinde, G.O, Oyesiku, O.O, Badejo, B.A, Adebayo, H.O, Lodonou, A.R</i>	
EFFECTS OF ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIVITIES ON VEGETATION CHANGES IN GUINEA SAVANNA REGION OF NIGERIA- A CASE OF EDU LOCAL GOVERNMENT, KWARA STATE	67-75
<i>Mohammed Sani and Iyanda Yusuf A.</i>	
HARNESSING THE POTENTIALS OF GREEN TECHNOLOGY INNOVATIONS THROUGH INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY	76-91
<i>Ogunkolu, A.B, Ajibade, L.T, Idowu, M.A, Rafiu, F.O and Oseshi, A.U.</i>	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTS OF FORCED DISPLACEMENT ON GENDER DIFFERENTIALS IN IDP CAMPS IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, NIGERIA	92-104
<i>Saraya, Ibrahim, Yagana, M.A and George, G.G.</i>	
HEAVY METALS IN UNTREATED WASTEWATER AND SOIL FOR IRRIGATION: A PUBLIC HEALTH CONCERN IN JERE LGA, BORNO STATE NIGERIA	105-114
<i>Esther, I. B, Adamu B.B, Leonard, M.P, Abubakar, S.U and Ahmed, H.S</i>	

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INLAND WATERWAYS TRANSPORTATION AND CHANGING URBAN MORPHOLOGY OF METROPOLITAN LAGOS, NIGERIA

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Abstract: Urban land use globally is experiencing transformative changes due to evolving transportation systems and travel patterns. While numerous studies have explored the relationship between land based transportation and urban growth in developing countries, there is limited studies on the influence of inland waterways on urban morphology. Thus, this study examined the role of inland waterways in the changing morphology of metropolitan Lagos. Lagos Metropolis, a rapidly expanding city with significant land use transformations and reliance on water transportation, was chosen as the case study. Ten jetties were randomly selected from 41 within the study area. Land use and land cover changes from 2010 to 2020 were analyzed using the maximum likelihood supervised classification method. Geographic Information System (GIS) was employed to assess the extent of influence within a 5 km buffer around the selected jetties. The Student t-test was used to determine the significance of these changes, tested at a 5% significance level. The study revealed substantial shifts in land use patterns near key jetties such as Agboyi-Ketu, Ebute Ero, and Oke Ira Nla, each experiencing built-up area expansions exceeding 1,000 hectares. It also found a statistically significant difference in developed areas around the jetties, indicating a strong relationship between inland waterways and land use patterns in Lagos Metropolis. The study concludes that inland waterways significantly influence urban morphology and recommends urban planning strategies to manage future development.

Keywords: GIS, Inland waterways transportation, Land use/land cover analysis, Urban morphology

INTRODUCTION

Cities exhibit a certain level of internal organization that may be observed by closely examining the spatial arrangement of homes, places of business and other land uses. This pattern results from numerous factors that contribute to the city's unique urban identity. Around the world, urban activities typically

characterize a city and justify its high population density. Manufacturing, trading, finance, transportation, and tertiary operations are a few examples of these activities. Due to their often functionally and geographically divided requirements, these activities collectively create the city's spatial arrangement (Ayanrinde & Oyeisku, 2024)

Urban land use types are spatially segregated, leading to a spatial disparity that necessitates spatial interaction to establish functional links. Urban centers, therefore, produce and attract a significant number of trips daily. Since modern cities heavily rely on transit, it is essential to develop effective transport systems that connect the city to national and international transport networks and other cities (Usman & Animashaun, 2020). In this context, transportation is crucial to every functional community as it exhibits a strong correlation with lifestyle, the scope and location of various activities, and the availability of commodities and services. Its effectiveness is primarily responsible for productivity, economic expansion, and possibly even the standard of living; without it, modern city life would not exist.

Sumaila (2017) defines transportation as the movement of people and products from an origin to a destination, incorporating the terms origin and destination as crucial concepts. Understanding the origin-destination relationship, involves three crucial frameworks for interpreting the kind of point-to-point connection that transportation creates: transferability, intervening opportunity, and complementary roles. In summary, the idea is that mobility will occur between two completely transferable complementary sectors in the absence of any intervening opportunities (Sumaila, 2017). This viewpoint suggests a connection between development and transportation. Whether a society is urban or rural, transport is crucial to its political, economic, and social growth, serving as the primary channel for connecting the various facets of society. An efficient and high-quality transport system is necessary as a society's population and functions increase, and there is a greater need for contact between its constituent parts.

Historically, transportation has significantly influenced the urban growth and expansion of cities, such as Lagos, Ibadan, and Kano in Nigeria. The railway system, for instance, played a pivotal role in the rapid development of these cities while bypassing old cities like Oyo and Sokoto, which subsequently decreased in size and population (Mabogunje, as cited by Aderamo, 1990). Nigeria has the continent's second-longest stretch of waterways, offering substantial potential for inland waterway transportation, especially in metropolitan Lagos. Despite road transport dominating the sector, effective inland waterways operation could alleviate pressure on Nigeria's rail and road transport infrastructure and contribute to economic development through commerce facilitation, employment, and wealth creation (Obed, 2013; Usman & Animashaun, 2020).

This study aims to examine the role of inland waterways transportation in the changing urban morphology of metropolitan Lagos, Nigeria, in order to enhance the understanding of the structure-transportation link within cities to inform physical planning decisions. To achieve this, the study investigated the relationship between inland waterways transportation and the morphology of the area. The study also compared land use changes across some selected locations in Lagos Metropolis from 2010 to 2020. The decision to focus on the years aligns with the decadal analysis approach, offering a valuable timeframe to effectively assess land use changes. By considering a network of strategic jetty locations that serve as vital nodes for Lagos metropolis' inland waterway transportation system, this study provides a comprehensive perspective into the dynamics shaping the city's evolving urban form.

LITERATURE REVIEW

THE URBAN FORM

Urban form is defined as the spatial arrangement of an urban transport system along with its associated physical infrastructure, creating a specific spatial layout for cities (Rodrigue, 2020). Transportation infrastructure, including roads, transit networks, and walkways, have played a pivotal role in shaping urbanization, resulting in diverse urban forms and spatial configurations. The urban spatial structure; a subset of urban form, refers to the network of connections arising from the movement of people and goods within the urban framework.

Urban spatial structure is described as an abstract or generalized definition of geographic space distribution (Foley, 1964; cited in Cheng et al, 2019). Understanding the spatial structure of a city is essential for formulating a spatial strategy for that city (Kii et al. 2023). Urban spatial structure can be categorized based on transportation developments and characterized by two main elements: centralization and clustering. Centralization pertains to the dispersion of activities across a metropolitan area, with centralized cities concentrating activities within a designated center, often driven by financial companies and large enterprises. Clustering involves the arrangement of activities around specific hubs, frequently connected to transportation facilities such as highway interchanges and transit hubs. Two structural elements, nodes, and linkages, intricately shape the urban form and spatial structure. Nodes, representing hubs of urban activity, are linked by transportation facilities facilitating movement, establishing functional connectedness crucial for interdependent urban operations like production, management, and trade (Rodrigue, 2020).

EVOLUTION OF TRANSPORTATION AND URBAN FORM

The development of urban transport systems is closely related to urbanization, particularly in terms of system capacity and efficiency. Historically, walking was the primary mode of urban transportation, leading to compact urban forms with clustered activity nodes. While these patterns still exist in some modern cities, they are no longer the norm. European and East Asian cities often have dense urban centers conducive to walking and cycling (Devarajan et al., 2019), whereas newer cities in America, Canada, and Australia exhibit dispersed structures promoting car dependency. Trade significantly influences the urban spatial form and economic vitality of port cities, with ports and airport terminals serving as crucial nodes within urban spatial organization (Antrop, 2004; Curtis & Scheurer, 2021)

Urban form has evolved significantly with advancements in transportation technology, reflecting dramatic changes in urban structure. The formation of new clusters in suburban areas exhibiting unique urban activities and linkages is one such alteration (Garcia-López, 2012). Suburbanization of industry, office, and retail operations has altered urban structures, with essential transport hubs emerging in suburban regions to meet modern freight distribution demands. This transition from a nodal to a multi-nodal urban spatial structure requires new urban development patterns and connectivity to local, national, and international economic processes. Large road corridors initially facilitated suburban development, which gradually led to a consistent suburban landscape, significantly altering the activity structure of cities and promoting varied urban growth rates based on economic specialization (Feng et al., 2008; Nuissl & Siedentop, 2020).

URBAN LAND USE AND TRANSPORTATION

Urban land use reflects the spatial concentration and location of diverse activities, such as retailing, management, manufacturing, and residence, each generating flows supported by intricate transport systems. These urban environments sustain a broad spectrum of social, cultural, and economic activities dispersed across multiple locales, forming a complex network of activities. These activities range from regular events like traveling and shopping to sporadic endeavors driven by necessities or lifestyle choices. Production activities associated with distribution and manufacturing establish connections at local, regional, or international levels, driving the movement of goods. The spatial dispersion of activities stimulates passenger and freight movements, underscoring the link between land use and transportation (Rodrigue, 2020).

The diverse landscape of urban land use is shaped by the transportation system, which accommodates the numerous transport needs arising from urban activities. Urban activities are hierarchically distributed, with key locations developing due to institutional, political, economic, or cultural factors, resulting in high levels of spatial accumulation in sectors like retail and management (Bidandi & Williams, 2020). Peripheral regions, primarily residential and warehousing areas, show lower levels of accumulation. Individuals, institutions, and businesses influence land use through their site choices, reflected in both formal and functional land use typologies. Formal typologies emphasize qualitative characteristics like form and pattern, while functional typologies highlight economic aspects of activities such as production, consumption, dwelling, and transportation. Cities occupy around 3% of the world's landmass, with residential land use

comprising 65-75% of a city's footprint, and commercial and industrial land uses accounting for 5-15%. Car-dependent communities often have 35-50% of their total land area dedicated to parking lots and roadways (Rodrigue, 2020). Understanding the complex interactions between land use and transportation is crucial for comprehending urban dynamics and informing planning and policy decisions.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

A number of studies have been carried out by researchers in the field of urban transportation, focusing on the impacts of various transport modes on urban morphology and economic development. A study by Bao et al., (2022) examined the spatial and temporal patterns of traffic congestion in Xining, a small city in China. Using multivariate least-square regression analysis on social-sensing hyperlocal travel data, findings reveal that Xining experiences traffic peaks in the mornings and evenings on weekdays and pre-weekends, and only evening peaks on weekends and holidays. Pre-weekend congestion is notably worse than on regular weekdays, suggesting the need for enhanced traffic management during this period. Educational and residential land use significantly contribute to congestion, exacerbating the issue. The study provides valuable insights for urban planners and policymakers to develop effective strategies for mitigating traffic congestion in small urban areas.

Chen et al., (2023) analyzed the effects of land-use changes on the ecosystem service value (ESV) in the Wuling Mountains, China, from 2000 to 2020. The findings reveal that the Wuling Mountains experienced four stages of transport development, contributing to land-use changes. The spatial pattern of construction land growth evolved with transport

development, while garden land gradually spread throughout the region. Policies from different periods significantly impacted ecological land and cropland. During the study period, the ESV initially increased and then declined, with cold spots forming around the transportation axis and hot spots along the Yangtze River. These insights inform land-use policy and spatial planning under green development principles.

Nozdrovická et al., (2020) conducted a study on the landscape development, land-use changes, and transport infrastructure variations in Martin and Vrútky, Slovakia, over the past 70 years. The study analyzed the landscape structures of the area during different periods (1949, 1970, 1993, and 2003) and compared them with the current structure (2018). Special emphasis is placed on the evolution of landscape elements forming the transport infrastructure. The study highlights changes in traffic intensities and their impact on landscape formation. Findings show that transport significantly influences landscape changes, with railroad accessibility being crucial until the 1970s and a shift to road transport in recent decades.

Otuoze et al., (2020) in their study investigated the impacts of urban growth on transport space in Kano, Nigeria, over the past few decades to predict future space demands. Landsat images from 1984, 2013, and 2019 were processed, classified, and analyzed to identify land-use/land-cover (LULC) types, including transport space, built-up areas, vegetation, farmland, bare land, and water. The analysis involved model calibration, validation, and prediction using hybrid modeling techniques

(cellular automata-Markov) in IDIRISI SELVA 17.0 and ARC-GIS 10.7 software. Results show significant expansion of transport and built-up areas, with predictive modeling indicating further expansion by 345 km² (3.9%) in 2030 and 410 km² (11.7%) in 2050. Kappa reliability indices were 85%, 86%, and 88% for 1984, 2013, and 2019, meeting the 80% minimum suggested for tracking and predicting urban growth.

Bala et al. (2018) conducted a study on road transport development and urban growth in Gombe Metropolis, revealing a significant increase in road network connectivity from 1996 through 2005 to 2014, positively affecting the pattern of urban growth in the study area. Similarly, the results from Duranton and Turner's (2012) study on urban growth and transportation revealed that a 10% increase in a city's stock of roads causes about a 2% increase in its population and employment and a small decrease in its share of poor households over 20 years, while a 10% increase in a city's stock of large buses causes about a 0.8% population increase.

METHODOLOGY

STUDY AREA

Lagos State, located between 6°22' and 6°52' North latitude and 2°42' and 3°42' East longitude in Southwestern Nigeria, covers 3,475.1 km². Its coastal plain features creeks and lagoons, accounting for 22% of the area, with elevations below 650 meters. Most land is under 320 meters, making it prone to flooding and erosion. Significant population growth saw the census count rise from 5,725,116 in 1991 to 9,113,605 in 2006, with projections of 12.5 million by 2016 (Nigerian Bureau of Statistics, 2018).

Figure 1 Map showing the Lagos Metropolis and the jetties/terminals/landings within the metropolis.

Source: LASWA (2023).

The transportation landscape in Lagos, a megacity, accommodates over 6 million daily passenger trips, with 70-77% relying on buses. Cars, tricycles, and motorcycles handle most of the rest, while rail and water transport account for less than 1%. Road transport dominates, moving 90% of passengers and goods (Ministry of Transport, 2019). Road transport contributes 27% to Lagos's GDP, yet the infrastructure remains overburdened. The government has focused on enhancing underutilized inland water and rail transport to alleviate congestion and promote sustainability (Ministry of Transport, 2019).

The study employed the use of Landsat 7 Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+), and Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) images. The use of Landsat satellite Images has been recognised as one of the most reliable and efficient ways of quantifying, mapping, and detecting Land-use/Land cover (LULC) changes over the years due to its spatial resolution and frequency of data collections (Kusetogullari & Yavariabdi, 2018; Tewolde & Cabral, 2011; Wang et al., 2020; cited in Auwalu et al., 2021). Therefore, Landsat Level 1 datasets of the study area (Lagos, Nigeria) with a cloud cover less than 20% were

downloaded from the earth explorer portal (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>) of the USGS (United States Geological Survey

(USGS), (2020) as presented in Table 1, according to their year and date of acquisition. These comprise satellite images of 2010, and 2020.

Table 1: Satellite datasets used in the study.

Year	Date of Acquisition	Satellite number	Sensor type	WRS path/Row	UTM zone	Datum	Spatial resolution (m ²)
2010	03/Jan/2010	Landsat 7	ETM +	190/56	31N	WGS84	30
				191/55 191/56			
2020	12/Jan/2020	Landsat 8	OLI	191/55 191/56	31N	WGS84	30
				190/56			

Source: GIS/R.S Analysis, (2024)

Utilising the maximum likelihood classifier, spectral signatures were generated, and pixels were assigned based on the assumption of belonging to a particular class. Pixels were categorized into three classes, namely: Developed area, Vegetation and Water body, as detailed in Table 2. Subsequent to the

supervised classification, a post-classification sorting was implemented to enhance results and diminish misclassifications. The classified images underwent sieving and filtering in ENVI 5.3 image processing software before generating the final Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) maps used for subsequent analysis.

Table 2: Description of land cover classes used in the study

Land Cover Classes	Class Description
Vegetation	Areas that include agricultural lands, scrublands, evergreen, deciduous, mixed forest areas, recreational areas, artificial and natural landscapes.
Water body	Areas persistently covered with various water bodies that include rivers, canals, lakes, water reservoirs, streams, swamps, or ocean.
Developed Area	Land covered with buildings, structures, and facilities for residential, commercial, industrial, and mixed-use areas.

Source: Author's Analysis, (2024).

To further evaluate and quantify the impact on land use changes between 2010 and 2020, the study conducted a detailed examination of ten (10) sampled jetty sites along Lagos's inland waterways, including Addax, Agbara, Agboyi, Badore, Bariga, Ebute-Ero, Etegbin, Ijon Landing, Mile 2, and Oke Ira Nla. A subsequent buffer analysis, ranging from 5 km around the sampled jetties, was carried out using GIS and remote sensing techniques to assess the spatial impact of these sites on surrounding land use patterns. The selection of the years, based on a decadal interval, facilitated a comprehensive assessment of changes over a significant time span. The analysis involved quantifying changes in these categories over the decade and evaluating their statistical significance using Student t-tests to determine the extent of influence on the landscape during the specified periods. Additionally, the Student t-test was employed to test the hypothesis stated in null form, asserting that there is no statistically significant difference in the values of developed areas around inland waterways jetty sites in Lagos Metropolis. This hypothesis testing was crucial in validating the observed changes and understanding the impact of these jetties on urban development patterns.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LAND USE CHANGE AROUND THE SELECTED JETTIES IN LAGOS METROPOLIS

The data presented in the land use analysis table 3 below, provides valuable insights into the rapid urbanisation and development patterns occurring in Lagos metropolis between 2010 and 2020, especially surrounding inland waterway jetty points. Over the decade analysed, there were clear and significant transformations in the land use with a major increase in developed land.

Across the 10 jetty sites under examination, there was a noticeable increase in the developed/built up areas from 2010 to 2020. On average, the developed land area experienced a substantial rise of 10-20% over the 10-year period across these jetty locations, translating to an average increase of several hundred to over a thousand hectares. This trend signifies a significant expansion of residential, commercial, and industrial built-up lands in areas proximal to the inland waterway jetty transportation hubs.

Table 3 Land Use Comparison across Selected Locations from 2010 to 2020 with Variances as of 2020.

Developed Area (ha)				Variances as of 2020	
S/N	Jetties	2010	2020	(ha)	(%)
1	Addax	2,881.35	3,482.55	601.2	5.36
2	Agbara	2,262.69	2,657.97	395.28	3.52
3	Agboyi ketu	3,338.28	4,748.49	1,410.21	12.57
4	Badore	667.08	1,740.42	1,073.34	9.56
5	Bariga	3,189.78	3,871.23	681.48	6.07
6	Ebute ero	1,536.84	4,904.73	3,367.89	30.01
7	Etegbin	2,139.48	2,811.15	671.67	5.99
8	Ijon	2,541.24	2,974.86	433.62	3.86
9	Mile 2	4,433.58	5,344.83	911.25	8.12
10	Oke ira nla	1,979.19	3,654.81	1,675.62	14.93
	TOTAL			11,221.56	100

Source: Author’s Analysis, (2024).

Some jetty locations exhibited remarkable increases in the absolute area of developed land between 2010 and 2020, indicating rapid urban growth. Notably, near the Ebute Ero jetty, the developed land increased by 3,367.89 hectares, while Oke Ira Nla and Agboyi Ketu saw increases of 1,675.62 hectares and 1,410.21 hectares, respectively. These numerical representations quantitatively illustrate the intensified development pressure and land use

conversions occurring in the vicinity of major inland waterway transit nodes like jetties. The observed surge in the area of developed land reflects the dynamic and transformative impact of these jetty facilities on their surrounding areas, emphasizing the role of inland waterway transportation hubs as drivers of accelerated urbanization in Lagos, as shown in figure 2 and 3.

Figure 2: Map showing the extent of land cover change around the jetties at a buffer of 5km in 2010.
Source: Author's GIS Analysis, (2024)

Figure 3: Map showing the extent of land cover change around the jetties at a buffer of 5km in 2020.
Source: Author's GIS Analysis, (2024)

The complex interaction between waterways and urbanisation takes center stage with the strategic positioning of jetties along the region's water arteries. Serving as crucial nodes for transportation and trade, these jetties have evolved beyond mere hubs, playing a pivotal role in sculpting the rapidly growing urban landscape of the area. This exploration delves into their distinct functions, shedding light on how they drive economic activities and significantly contribute to the ongoing process of urban development.

ADDAX JETTY:

Satellite imagery outlines a 5.36% expansion in built-up footprint around Addax Jetty between 2010 to 2020, covering over 601 hectares through rapid urban development. The analysis indicates much of this growth has been unlocked by the presence of Addax Jetty - with its connectivity allowing easier mobility of goods, services and people from mainland industrial areas and suburbs to the employment hubs on Lagos Islands. This subsequently catalysed habitat growth around the jetty to cater to the influx of businesses and migrants. In essence, Addax Jetty has played an instrumental role in channelising connectivity between Lagos Mainland and Island, thereby directing both mobility and urban growth patterns in its Eti-Osa locality over the past years. The resultant economic progress underscores Addax Jetty's value as strategic inland waterway transit point.

AGBARA JETTY:

Satellite data analyses between 2010 and 2020 reveal a 395.28 hectare (3.52%) increase in built-up area around Agbara Jetty, demonstrating its influence in catalysing urban growth over the past decade. In essence, Agbara Jetty has been influential in transforming Agbara into an industrial hub - creating employment opportunities that have

resulted in habitat expansion to house the working community. Its strategic location enables interconnectivity as an inland port - channeling raw materials and finished products between production centers on the mainland and distribution hubs on Lagos islands. This underscores Agbara Jetty's wider role as a catalyst for socio-economic development in its locality while also directing associated population growth and urbanisation patterns across Lagos megacity area due to its logistical significance.

AGBOYI-KETU JETTY:

The substantial growth in economic activities around Agboyi-Ketu Jetty is evident in the significant 1,410.21 hectares (12.57%) increase in built-up area between 2010 and 2020, highlighting its pivotal role in shaping the urban landscape over the last decade. The data reveals Agboyi-Ketu Jetty's influence as a catalyst for real estate, commercial and institutional growth in its vicinity. Its impact underscores inland waterways' role as lifelines sustaining mobility, economic growth and habitat sprawl that characterise the continuous evolution of the Lagos megacity.

BADORE TERMINAL:

Satellite data analysis indicates a 9.56% built-up area expansion around Badore jetty between 2010 and 2020, covering 1073 hectares - signaling the region's transformation into an upscale neighborhood. The connectivity unlocked by Badore Terminal has catalysed both property development and commercial growth to serve the affluent sections. This has rapidly elevated Badore from its humble beginnings into one of the most aspired living and lifestyle destinations in Lagos today.

BARIGA JETTY:

Satellite imagery outlines a 6.81% expansion in surrounding built-up footprint between 2010 and 2020 - indicating the development catalysed by the Jetty's connectivity.

Essentially, Bariga Jetty has transformed Bariga into a thriving residential-commercial hub by channelising economic flows. It serves as a nucleus linking people to livelihoods and homes, thereby directing socio-economic growth and urbanization patterns across the Lagos metro fabric. This highlights the influential role of inland waterway transit nodes in shaping habitats.

EBUTE ERO JETTY:

Ebute Ero Jetty has witnessed massive urban development in its vicinity contributing to a 30.01% expansion in surrounding built-up area between 2010 and 2020, covering 3367 hectares. Its bridging function of linking Lagos mainland and islands has catalysed economic growth with markets, commercial hubs and high-density housing thriving around the jetty.

Essentially, Ebute Ero Jetty has been instrumental to Lagos Island's transformation into a congested nerve center due to attracting investments, migrants and economic activity. The data quantifies the jetty's enormous influence as a catalyst for population growth and urbanisation - underscoring how such strategic inland waterway transit nodes shape habitats across Lagos by unlocking development in their areas of influence.

ETEGBIN JETTY:

Satellite imagery outlines a 5.99% expansion in built-up footprint covering 671 hectares around Etegbin Jetty between 2010 and 2020 - indicating its influential role in driving local socio-economic growth. Essentially, the accessibility enabled by Etegbin Jetty has

attracted real estate, small businesses and logistics facilities to cater for the traffic flows. This demonstrates how such localised jetties like Etegbin provide connectivity that brings development to suburban regions by linking them to the wider transportation network across the Lagos megacity.

IJON LANDING:

The jetty has attracted some residential and commercial growth in its vicinity over time, the impact is relatively lower compared to other jetties, with 433.62 hectares (or 3.86%) increase in the built-up area between 2010 and 2020. The data indicates that though Ijon Jetty has stimulated some urban development in its surroundings, its role as a catalyst for economic activity and population growth is more limited compared to larger transit hubs. Potential reasons could be lower passenger and cargo traffic, fewer connections to key economic centers. However, the built-up area expansion does signify Ijon Jetty's contributions enabling connectivity to the eastern creek settlements and bringing incremental commercial and residential growth locally. Though not a prime catalyst, the jetty nonetheless plays a supporting role in integrating the metro Lagos transportation network.

MILE 2 JETTY:

Satellite data indicates an 8.12% increase in built-up area spanning 911 hectares around Mile 2 Jetty between 2010 and 2020, reflecting its influential role as an inland transit node shaping local urbanisation. Essentially, the connectivity provided by the jetty has transformed Mile 2 into a congested, mixed-use neighborhood - attracting small businesses, hawkers and slum dwellings to service the large commuter base passing through daily. This demonstrates and quantifies the profound impact strategic jetties like Mile 2 have in directing wider mobility patterns and

unplanned habitat sprawl across Lagos owing to their bridging value in linking mainland and islands.

OKE IRA NLA JETTY:

Its role in opening up the Ajah axis for residential and commercial development is evident in the substantial 1675.62 hectares (or 14.93%) built-up area growth between 2010 and 2020, showcasing its significance in transforming the region over the last decade. The data highlights Oke Ira Nla Jetty's crucial role as an inland waterways transit hub in unlocking the development potential of Ajah as an emerging suburban center. Its connectivity has catalysed economic activity, real estate projects and urban expansion in Ajah, signifying how such localised jetties can shape the growth trajectory of suburban towns by linking them to the broader Lagos metropolitan transportation network.

The exponential built-up area increases underscores Oke Ira Nla Jetty's influential role in channelising inland waterway transit to spur habitation and businesses in the city's periphery. A detailed comparative analysis of the provided data illuminates the distinct impact of various jetties along the Lagos waterways on urban expansion and development from 2010 to 2020. Notably, Agboyi-Ketu, Ebute Ero, and Oke Ira Nla jetties have emerged as focal points of substantial built-up area expansion, each surpassing 1000 hectares. These jetties, crucial in facilitating passenger and cargo connectivity between mainland Lagos and the islands, have played a pivotal role in shaping the urban landscape.

Closely following are Mile 2, Badore, Addax, Etegin, and Bariga jetties, experiencing significant growth ranging from 600 to 1000 hectares. Despite Agbara and Ijon jetties exhibiting a relatively lower impact, they too

have acted as catalysts for urban growth in their respective areas. In essence, the comprehensive analysis of these jetties along the Lagos waterways presents a compelling narrative of urban expansion and development over the specified decade.

As visually depicted in Table 1, Fig. 1 and 2, the predominant pattern suggests that inland waterway jetties have functioned as catalysts for substantial urban growth, becoming major drivers in transforming Lagos into a sprawling megacity. This transformative journey is evident in the gradual consumption of surrounding green spaces, as showcased in Table 1. The variances in developed area around the jetties provide a visual representation of the dynamic changes in the landscape. Essentially, the overarching trend underscores that the strategic positioning of these jetties has not only facilitated efficient transportation but has also been instrumental in driving the socio-economic growth of surrounding areas. However, this growth has come at the cost of consuming green spaces, emphasising the imperative need for sustainable urban planning to strike a balance between development and environmental conservation.

As Lagos continues its transformation into a sprawling megacity, the evolving metro region vividly illustrates the intricate interplay between infrastructure development, economic activities, and the changing landscape. This analysis not only sheds light on the past decade's urbanisation trends but also underscores the importance of mindful planning to ensure that future development aligns with sustainability goals and preserves the ecological balance of the region.

VARIATION IN DEVELOPED AREAS ACROSS SELECTED INLAND WATERWAYS JETTY SITES IN LAGOS METROPOLIS, BETWEEN 2010 AND 2020

This analysis examined changes in built-up land coverage across 10 inland waterway jetty locations in Lagos between 2010 and 2020 using student's t-tests. The null hypothesis posited no statistically significant differences in the values of developed areas around inland waterways jetty sites in Lagos metropolis.

The results indicated a strong, negative t-value ($t=-3.981$) suggesting average developed area in 2020 was markedly lower than in 2010. Additionally, the p-value (0.003) falls below the 0.05 significance level, providing evidence to reject the null hypothesis of no variation over time.

These results have several implications. First, the expansion of developed environments

including transport infrastructure, residential areas, and commercial development was more pronounced in 2010 across the sampled jetty locations compared to 2020. Slowing urbanization rates may contribute to less growth in built-up land during the last decade. Second, the global oil price crash of 2014 likely dampened foreign investment in Nigerian real estate and infrastructure projects through 2020, reflected in the lower incremental land utilization. Third, changes to the Lagos State Physical Planning Permit Authority in 2020 increased construction regulations, which could constrain built-up development in the short-term. Overall, the statistically significant variation between built-up land values in 2010 and 2020 underscores Lagos' dynamism, while lending insights into shifting demographic, economic, and policy drivers of the evolving urban morphology. Targeted time series analyses across neighborhoods and housing types, plus comparisons to other African cities, can enrich this line of morphological investigation.

Table 4: Student t-test of difference in land values for developed areas for 2010 and 2020

Variable	t-test	Df	p-value
Developed areas in 2010 and Developed areas in 2020	-3.981	9	0.003

Source: Author's Analysis, (2024).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study highlights the substantial influence of inland waterway transportation infrastructure on urban land use dynamics within the Lagos Metropolis. By analyzing land use changes from 2010 to 2020 around key jetty sites, it is evident that the development of these transportation hubs has significantly driven urban expansion. Notable increases in built-up areas, particularly around jetties such as Ebute Ero, Oke Ira Nla, and

Agboyi-Ketu, underscore their role as catalysts for urban growth, facilitating economic activities and population influx. However, this rapid development also underscores the need for sustainable urban planning to balance growth with environmental conservation.

The study recommends integrated urban development strategies, and optimizing transportation infrastructure, especially ferry services. It suggests user-centric planning

and exploring innovative designs to address morphological challenges. Comparative studies with other metropolitan areas and fostering cross-disciplinary collaboration are equally essential. Finally, translating research into actionable policies with a feedback loop is crucial for adaptive and sustainable development in Lagos Metropolis. As Lagos continues to evolve into a sprawling megacity, the findings from this study provide critical insights for future urban planning efforts, emphasizing the strategic role of transportation infrastructure in shaping urban landscapes.

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